

The Experimental Performance of Wastewater Trap Model A

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Abstract:

The paper aims to study the hydraulic performance through a wastewater trap using vortex phenomena. The wastewater trap model A (WTA) was intended for sedimentation and floatables from the wastewater drainage system. It was designed in 2014 and laboratorial studied in detail at Edith Cowan University testing three different scales of WTA: WTA1, WTA2 and WTA3. As model A is a gravitational model where gravitational forces are the most important, the Froude numbers in model and prototype must be the same. From results obtained, the analysis revealed that head loss increases proportionally with flow rates and scale sizes. Head loss coefficient, water level and Reynolds number at different flow rates are also presented.

Keywords: Head Loss, Head Loss Coefficient, Water Level, Reynolds Number.

Introduction:

With continued global population growth and expansion of industrial businesses, an increasing amount of wastewater is produced which cannot meet the basic requirements set out by local and national governing authorities. A significant source of this pollution is contaminated sediments, chemicals and oils that are used to conduct business activities on the commercial premises (Wong, 2000). Surface run off the water which drains in to the urban stormwater drainage systems picking up sediment along the way can also cause a catastrophic effect to the receiving water bodies (Scholz & Yazdi, 2009). This is causing major problems and removing these pollutants to prevent them from entering valuable downstream systems is essential to revitalising impaired water bodies, sustaining their good ecological status and preventing any further harm. Additionally, In Western Australia, a large amount of the drinking water is collected from beneath urban environments, so it is in the community's best interest to keep wastewater quality as clean as possible (Department of Environment, 2004).

Significance:

General awareness of worldwide environmental issues has led to the increasing implementation of national and local wastewater reduction policies applying to industrial businesses (Mehta, 2007). Wastewater quality needs to be maintained at an acceptable of cleanliness before discharging into the drainage line for primary treatment or reuse on the business premises (Victoria, 2009). There is many reason why unauthorised industrial wastewater disposal in to the drainage system is illegal such as corroding, damaging or blocking pipes and equipment being used in the wastewater treatment systems, toxic materials contaminating sludge's causing more expense to the local authority to dispose, threat to the health of workers within the wastewater system and contaminates not being filtered out of the treatment process (Australian Water & Wastewater Association, 1994). As significant amounts of organic and inorganic pollutants are bound to sediment, not treating the wastewater and allowing flow in to our stormwater system can cause a decrease in the availability of light and oxygen in the water column which in turn creates a rise in toxic algae species. Toxic contaminants such as heavy metals immediate impact are the death of organisms such as the biofilters used to treat drainage wastewater, while the long-term impacts are associated with contaminants through the food chain due to pollution of the receiving waterbody (Hosja, 1994).

While there are multiple products related to the preliminary separation of sediment, suspended solids, heavy metals and immiscible liquids removal before disposal in the main drainage system, there is still limited research or information on a simple cost effective cylindrical vortex separators. Due to this, a new cylindrical wastewater trap model A has been designed as a preliminary physical separator to suit industrial and commercial premises.

Experimental Test Procedure:

The wastewater trap model A was designed to remove solids and liquids pollutants from the wastewater drainage systems. It is a simple cylindrical vortex separator with a small tweak compared to the standard

design. The design is comprised of three main components; inlet, outlet and cylindrical or vortex chamber. A graphical representation of the hydrodynamic vortex separator design is shown in figure 1. Although the size, shape, chamber and complexity of vortex separators may differ between each model, the basic principles are the same as a traditional simple vortex separator. In this study, the water is injected into the inlet pipe which is orientated tangentially to the cylindrical chamber. This creates a radial swirling motion within the vortex chamber and as the water spins around, sediments and heavy solids gather at the bottom centre of the chamber. Additionally, any buoyant pollutants or oils should be theoretically kept or trapped above the outlet pipe elbow. Expected pure water will exit out via 'L' 90-degree bend (elbow) of the outlet pipe located inside the vortex chamber and then out to the downstream system. One major design tweak that this vortex separator has over a traditional design which may or may not separate light pollutants better than a traditional design.

Figure 1: Wastewater Trap Model A

Three physical scale models of WTA have been designed and experimentally tested at ECU hydraulic laboratory. The dimensions of the WTA, heights, inlet and outlet pipes are given in table 1. Inlet and outlet pipes are elevated at the middle height of each vortex chamber model. For each scale model, the hydraulic characteristics performance will be determined for multiple flow rates replicating the VersaTarp type W testing method (figure 2).

Table 1: Dimensions for all Wastewater Trap Model A Scales.

	Scale 1 Model A1	Scale 2 Model A2	Scale 4 Model A3
Inlet Pipe Diameter (mm)	25	50	100
Outlet Pipe Diameter (mm)	25	50	100
Vortex Chamber Diameter (mm)	150	300	600
Vortex Chamber Height (mm)	300	600	1200

Figure 2: Experimental Setup Diagram

Results and Discussion:

All scale models of wastewater trap model A were subjected to a range of proper hydraulic characteristics performance testing. The corresponding head loss, head loss coefficient water levels and Reynolds number were determined at each flow rate while the chamber is open to the air. This interprets enough information and specification for this type of separator in the actual field (Ismail et al, 2006).

Head loss:

The pressure head between inlet and outlet was measured by using a manometer to find out the head loss at all flow rates. Bernoulli equation was used to achieve the head loss. Although the wastewater traps model A has been designed without having baskets or filter membrane, the head loss is found reasonably high compared to VTW. Figures 3, 4 and 5 show the same pattern relationship between head loss and flow rates and inlet velocities, head loss increases proportionally with the flow rates. It is started from 12 mm at 0.02 l/s to reach the maximum 150 mm at 0.22 l/s for model A1, from 16 mm at 0.07 to 363 mm at 1.84 l/s for model A2 and from 30 mm at 1.3 l/s to 600 mm at 9 l/s for model A3.

Figure 3: Relationship Between Head Loss & Flow Rate – Model A1

Figure 4: Relationship Between Head Loss & Flow Rate - Model A2

Figure 5: Relationship Between Head Loss Flow Rate - Model A3

Head Loss Coefficient:

The head loss coefficient (K_e) was also achieved at all flow rates by calculating the ratio of energy loss to the equivalent full pipe velocity head at the inlet pipe (Ismail & Nikraz, 2008). As shown in figure 6, the head loss coefficient is inversely proportional to the flow rate at first flows where the inlet pipe is partially full and then becomes constant once the pipe gets full. It is raised from the highest value of 123 at 0.02 l/s and then decreased to a constant value of 13 from 0.1 l/s onwards. Figures 7 and 8 show similar relationships but with fewer K_e values of 8. Because of the outlet pipe elbow, the head loss coefficient is proven to be very high compared to VersaTraps models.

Figure 6: Relationship Between Head Loss Coefficient and Flow Rate - Model A1

Figure 7: Relationship Between Head Loss Coefficient and Flow Rate - Model A2

Figure 8: Relationship Between Head Loss Coefficient and Flow Rate - Model A3

Water Level:

The water level in the vortex chamber has been measured at five points which are shown in figure 9. Due to vortex phenomena applied, water levels are found to have the same values at the first four points however it is a bit lower at the centre point (5). From figures 10, 11, and 12, water level curves have a slight gap at low flow rates and this gap increases proportionally with the increase of flow rate and scale size.

Figure 9: Locations for Water Levels Measurement Points

Figure 10: Water Level at all Flow Rates - Model A1

Figure 11: Water Level at all Flow Rates - Model A2

Figure 12: Water Level at all Flow Rates - Model A3

Reynolds Number:

In order to achieve high trapping efficiency for any type of separator, Reynolds number (Re) must be considered and measured. It has been reported that Re is very important to describe the transportation of particles in a fluid (Rapp, 2017). Graphs in figures 13, 14 and 15 show a linear relationship between Re with the flow rate or inlet velocity. On model WTA1, Re is begun with a laminar flow 1,200 to reach a turbulent flow 12,000 at the maximum flow rate however it is started in a transitional flow on models WTA2 and WTA3 and respectively reached 50,000 and 130,000 at the maximum flow rates.

Figure 13: Reynolds Number at all Flow Rates - Model A1

Figure 14: Reynolds Number at all Flow Rates - Model A2

Figure 15: Reynolds Number at all Flow Rates - Model A3

Conclusion:

The paper was focused on a new design of wastewater trap type A by means of their hydraulic performance using vortex phenomena. The full investigation was achieved by conducting an experimental study for three different scales of WTA. From hydraulic graphs, the head loss for all scales is found to increase proportionally as the flow rate increases. Furthermore, it increases with the increase of the scale size with the same curve pattern. The head loss coefficient shows the same pattern in all scales with slightly different values. Comparing these values to other traps such as VresaTraps, it is quietly higher. Water levels are also measured and shown lower value at the center point and the difference between point 5 and the rest of the points increases as the flow rate increases. Reynolds number is obtained to increase linearly with the flow rate and scale sizes to reach a very high turbulent flow at model WTA3.

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